

THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGIC WOMEN AND GIRLS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THINKING OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract. This article is about the role of female pedagogues in the development of young people's thinking, as well as in the development of their creative thinking, the role of female pedagogues in the formation of cognitive and creative relations, the pedagogical and psychological enrichment of the formation of professional moral and moral personal moral and ethical characteristics of female pedagogues. given.

Key words: idea, goal, support, task, planning, skill, modern, knowledge, education, training, student, thinking, logic.

РОЛЬ ПЕДАГОГОВ И ДЕВУШЕК В РАЗВИТИИ МЫШЛЕНИЯ МОЛОДЕЖИ

Аннотация. В данной статье речь идет о роли женщин-педагогов в развитии мышления молодежи, а также в развитии их творческого мышления, роли женщин-педагогов в формировании познавательных и творческих отношений, педагогическом и психологическом обогащении образования. профессионально-нравственно-нравственных лично-нравственно-этических характеристик женщин-педагогов. данный.

Ключевые слова: идея, цель, опора, задача, планирование, умение, современное, знание, образование, обучение, ученик, мышление, логика.

Since we have set ourselves the great goal of building the foundations of the Third Renaissance in our country, for this we must create the environment and conditions that will further develop the professional spiritual and moral and personal spiritual and moral characteristics of our female teachers. In this regard, we need to further develop education and training. Then we can achieve our goal by advancing science and innovation. On the way to this goal, our pedagogues should set great goals and work hard to achieve them.

Only then, through the actions of pedagogues, our children will become a great and powerful force that will realize the age-old dreams and hopes of our people. To this end, female educators should mobilize all their strength and capabilities to implement large-scale reforms based on the idea that "New Uzbekistan starts from the threshold of the school, from the educational system." Our pedagogues are responsible for raising young people to become independent and rational thinkers, possessing noble qualities based on modern knowledge and experiences, national and universal values. The experience of the world shows that the investment spent on raising the young generation to adulthood in all respects will bring ten or a hundred times more benefits to the society. It was not for nothing that our great grandfather Abu Ali Ibn Sina said a thousand years ago, "Courageous and brave people are not afraid of the difficulties that will happen in the future." In our country, comprehensive reforms aimed at the interests of the people are being carried out within the framework of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, developed at the initiative of the head of our state. 5 important initiatives aimed at wide involvement of young

people in culture, art and physical education and sports, formation of skills of efficient use of information technologies, widespread promotion of reading, increasing employment of women are being effectively implemented. Based on the relevance of the research mentioned above, it should be noted that the development of any state and society depends on the development of education and its organizers.

At this point, it should be noted that from a pedagogical and psychological point of view, when thinking about the forms, types, characteristics, and essence of thinking, all the things that a person perceives and keeps in his memory have a certain meaning and essence for him. . So, the basis of our understanding of the world and its secrets lies in the level of personal connection and significance of things and events for us. In psychology, the cognitive process related to our understanding, understanding and expressing our conscious attitude towards it is called thinking. Thinking is a form of generalized and abstracted reflection that ensures the presence of complex, comprehensive connections between things and events that are considered objects of knowledge of the human mind. For a long time, the problems of thinking, with their complexity, eluded the attention of psychologists, it was considered a matter for philosophers and logicians to think about. These issues really show the complex nature of thinking and thought processes. But even so, it should be noted that, firstly, thinking and thinking processes are cognitive processes; secondly, they are also a form of reflection of existence by a person, a form of generalization and indirect reflection; thirdly, these processes are also studied by experimental psychology; fourthly, thinking is the highest and highest form of knowledge.

For example, Ibn Sina, Alisher Nawai, Abu Nasr Farabi, Al-Farghani, Khorezmi, Zamakhshari, scholars such as Ibn Sina, Alisher Nawai, Al-Farghani, Khorezmi, Zamakhshari, etc., are proof of the importance and immortality of the ideas and discoveries created at the time of their creation. and admitted. The reason for this is the painstaking and tireless work of our scholars in the world of science.

Because the creator or the discoverer wants to discover something, he searches tirelessly, but he does not know when, under what conditions, in what way he can discover it. In order to develop such creativity, creativity, and creative activity in the minds of our youth, our pedagogues must take into account the individual characteristics of young people. Because motives of social behavior and personal motivation are important in the creative process. Our pedagogues, who carry out such activities, expand the creative thinking and knowledge of young people and arm them with new concepts and views, develop their creative thinking by applying best practices to the teaching process, and have the right attitude towards psychological ideas and social relations. to acquire the skills and competencies that form the appropriate creative thinking, to teach the theoretical-methodological, natural-scientific foundations aimed at developing creative thinking in the minds of young people, to make young people able to express cognitive and creative approaches in existing problem situations and the correct reaction to social realities should be formed.

In conclusion, we can say that, like all the reforms being implemented in our country, the content of the state policy on youth is important because it focuses on the development of young people into all-round well-rounded personnel with creative thinking potential. This, in turn, will help young people to become mature personnel in the future and to grow up as professionals who are in line with the interests of the state and society.

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